

PERTURBATIONS IN THE MICROBIAL BALANCE ASSOCIATED WITH ACUTE RESPIRATORY VIRAL INFECTIONS AND ANTIBIOTIC THERAPY**Semenov Y.,***Student of Medical Faculty**I. Horbachevsky Ternopil National Medical University, Ternopil, Ukraine***Semenova I.,***PhD, MD**Radiologist, Hemomedica Ternopil LLC, Ternopil, Ukraine***Kravets N.***PhD, Associate Professor of the Department of Microbiology, Virology and Immunology**I. Horbachevsky Ternopil National Medical University, Ternopil, Ukraine**ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-7593-1753>***Abstract**

To determine the characteristics of bacterial colonisation of the nasopharynx in patients according to history of acute respiratory viral infection (ARVI) and use of antibiotic therapy within the previous three months. The study was conducted at the Department of Microbiology, Virology, and Immunology of I. Horbachevsky Ternopil National Medical University. In a prospective clinical trial, 57 patients were divided into three groups: Group I - without ARVI and antibiotic therapy; Group II - after ARVI, without antibiotic therapy; Group III - after ARVI with antibiotic therapy. Classical bacteriological methods were used to assess the nasopharyngeal microbiota. Statistical analysis was performed using one-way ANOVA and Tukey HSD test. Group III showed a significant decrease in the concentration of *Staphylococcus spp.*, *Corynebacterium spp.*, and *Streptococcus spp.* ($p < 0.05$), along with an increase in *Staphylococcus aureus* levels and the emergence of *Streptococcus pyogenes*. Group II demonstrated intermediate values between Groups I and III, indicating the impact of both ARVI and antibiotic therapy on the nasopharyngeal microbiota. A history of ARVI leads to statistically significant alterations in the nasopharyngeal microbiocenosis. Antibiotic use is associated with more profound disturbances of the normal microbiota and an increased carriage of *Staphylococcus aureus*, which may indicate a risk of developing antibiotic resistance.

Keywords: nasopharynx, microbiota, ARVI, antibiotic therapy, *Staphylococcus aureus*.

Introduction

The nasopharyngeal microbiota plays a critical role in maintaining the barrier function of the upper respiratory tract mucosa and in the development of local and systemic immune responses [1]. Alterations in the composition of the normal microbiota may promote colonisation by pathogenic microorganisms and increase the risk of complications from infectious diseases [2]. Of particular interest are the frequent cases of acute respiratory viral infections (ARVI), which are among the most common reasons for seeking primary care [3]. Treatment of ARVI patients often involves the prescription of antibiotics, sometimes without clinical justification, which may have adverse effects on the microbiocenosis of the mucous membranes [4].

Among the key issues requiring further investigation is the effect of ARVI and antibiotic use on the composition of the nasopharyngeal microbiota, in particular the carriage rates of opportunistic and pathogenic bacteria such as *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Staphylococcus spp.*, *Streptococcus spp.*, *Corynebacterium spp.* and *Streptococcus pyogenes* [5]. Investigating these aspects is particularly important in view of the increasing prevalence of antibiotic resistance, which remains a major challenge in modern medicine [6, 7]. The aim of this study was to evaluate changes in the bacterial colonisation of the nasopharynx in relation to the history of ARVI and the use of antibiotics within the previous three months. The results provide a better understanding of the relationship between upper respiratory tract infections, rational antibiotic use and the status of the nasopharyngeal microbiocenosis.

Materials and Methods

The study was conducted at the Department of Microbiology, Virology and Immunology, I. Horbachevsky Ternopil National Medical University, Ministry of Health of Ukraine. It was designed as an open-label, prospective, cohort, comparative clinical trial. A total of 57 patients were studied and divided into three groups according to clinical and gender criteria: Group I ($n=18$): patients who had neither suffered from ARVI nor received antibiotic therapy in the previous three months; Group II ($n=20$): patients who had suffered from ARVI in the previous three months without receiving antibiotic therapy; Group III ($n=19$): patients who had suffered from ARVI and received antibiotic therapy in the previous three months. Exclusion criteria were oncological diseases, acute and exacerbated chronic diseases of vital organs, severe diabetes mellitus (DM) and type 1 DM. The mean age of the patients was 44.50 ± 18.83 years (range 18-75 years); there were 29 females (50.88%) and 28 males (49.12%).

Nasopharyngeal swabs were taken from the posterior wall of the nasopharynx using a sterile disposable swab. Patients abstained from the use of nasal drops, nasal irrigation, and food and drink for 3-4 hours prior to sampling, which was performed in the fasting state or at least 3-4 hours after eating.

Classical bacteriological methods were used to examine the nasopharyngeal swabs, including quantitative plating on differential diagnostic media and subsequent identification to genus level based on morphological, cultural and biochemical characteristics.

Normality of the sample distribution was assessed using the Shapiro-Wilk test. Data were expressed as means with standard errors ($M \pm m$). Bacterial counts were expressed as decimal logarithms. Statistical hypotheses were rejected at a significance level (p) of less than 0.05. Differences between independent sample means were assessed using one-way ANOVA followed

by the post-hoc Tukey HSD (honestly significant difference) test.

Data were processed using Microsoft Excel 2016 (Microsoft), STATISTICA® 8.0 (StatSoft Inc., USA) and IBM® SPSS® Statistics version 16.0.

Results

Indicators of nasopharyngeal bacterial colonisation in the study groups are shown in Table 1.1.

Table 1.

Indicators of nasopharyngeal bacterial colonisation in the groups studied

Indicator	Group I (n=18)	Group II (n=20)	Group III (n=19)
<i>Staphylococcus spp.</i> , lg CFU/mL	1.97±0.12*	1.11±0.15*	0.57±0.17*
<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i> , lg CFU/mL	0.87±0.11*	1.25±0.14*	1.95±0.12*
<i>Corynebacterium spp.</i> , lg CFU/mL	0.95±0.15	0.97±0.14	0.44±0.17*
<i>Streptococcus spp.</i> , lg CFU/mL	1.37±0.07	1.41±0.09	0.61±0.18*
<i>Streptococcus pyogenes</i> , lg CFU/mL	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	0.45±0.20*

*Note: * - statistically significant differences between groups according to one-way ANOVA and post-hoc Tukey HSD test ($p < 0.05$).

The lowest concentration of *Staphylococcus spp.* Was observed in Group III ($p < 0.05$), indicating the negative effect of antibiotic therapy on the concentration of non-pathogenic staphylococci in the nasopharynx. Group II showed a significantly higher concentration compared to Group III ($p < 0.05$), but significantly lower compared to Group I ($p < 0.05$), suggesting an effect of ARVI on changes in the nasopharyngeal bacterial flora. *Staphylococcus aureus* colonization was significantly highest in Group III ($p < 0.05$), indicating a negative effect of antibiotic use on *S. aureus* carriage and a possible contribution to the development of antibiotic resistance. The lowest values were found in Group I ($p < 0.05$). Group II showed intermediate values, significantly different from both groups I and III ($p < 0.05$).

Concentrations of *Streptococcus spp.* And *Corynebacterium spp.* Were lowest in group III, demonstrating the negative effect of antibiotics on these bacteria ($p < 0.05$). There was no significant difference in the concentration of *Corynebacterium spp.* Between Groups I and II ($p > 0.05$).

Streptococcus pyogenes was only detected in Group III, suggesting that antibiotic therapy may disrupt the normal microbiota and promote colonization by pathogenic bacteria.

The proportion of *Staphylococcus aureus* carriers was significantly highest in Group III ($p < 0.05$), supporting the hypothesis that antibiotics may indirectly contribute to the development of antibiotic-resistant strains under clinical conditions. In Addition, Group II had a significantly higher proportion of carriers than Group I but lower than Group III ($p < 0.05$), confirming the effect of ARVI itself on *S. aureus* carriage.

Conclusions

It was established that a history of ARVI leads to statistically significant changes in the nasopharyngeal microbiota, particularly regarding *Staphylococcus spp.*, *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Corynebacterium spp.*, *Streptococcus spp.*, and *Streptococcus pyogenes* ($p < 0.05$). Antibiotic therapy in patients with ARVI results in

more profound disruption of the normal microbiota and an increased risk of *Staphylococcus aureus* carriage, potentially contributing to the development of antibiotic resistance.

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